

Are sleepwalkers philosophical zombies? Insights and predictions from a quantum model of consciousness

Andrew Bell

Eccles Institute of Neuroscience
John Curtin School of Medical Research
The Australian National University
Canberra, ACT 2601
Australia

Abstract:

A recent quantum model of consciousness proposes that neuronal clusters in the cortex switch from being an unconscious neural computer (when asleep) to a conscious quantum computer (when awake). The transition relies on feedback cooling, and is not unlike how a conductor becomes a superconductor when cooled. Here the model is explored in the context of sleepwalking, a peculiar but common phenomenon that has largely escaped philosophical attention. Based on several remarkable accounts, the case is made that sleepwalkers are truly philosophical zombies: they execute complex behaviour while remaining completely unconscious. They are phenomenal blanks, acting out pre-programmed routines governed by their neural computer. But when feedback cooling is active, the same neural circuits acquire macroscopic quantum coherence, and the sleepwalker awakes and becomes conscious. The claim under test is that if zombies exist, materialism must be false, for there is something – the mind – over and above the body.

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Introduction

Why are we conscious? And what is it that makes us conscious? These are the notoriously ‘hard’ questions of consciousness (Chalmers, 1995, 1996), and philosophers have grappled with them since philosophy began.

Here these questions are examined in the light of a novel quantum mechanical theory of phenomenal consciousness which relies on feedback cooling to overcome the limitations imposed by thermal noise; as a result, a coherent, macroscale quantum state is created that might be identified with consciousness itself (Bell, 2023).

The goal of the present paper is to gain a better understanding of consciousness by comparing cases of it being present – when a person is awake – with cases of when it is absent – as, it is argued, in cases of sleepwalking. In terms of the new model, the claim is made that the crucial difference is whether or not feedback cooling is switched on or off within cortical minicolumns, a process that creates coherent quantum states extending over the whole of the cortex, not unlike what happens when a conductor is cooled and becomes a superconductor. In the case of cortical cooling, the resulting macroscopic coherent state can be equated with the conscious human mind.

By consciousness is meant phenomenal consciousness, laden with qualia (Klein, 2021), not just access consciousness (Block 1995). A nice working definition of consciousness is the *here-I-am-ness* of Dennett (2013). It is plainer English than the difficult “something that it is like to be” of Nagel (1974). Further, Nagel’s wording has difficulty capturing meditational states which are “not like anything” (Shear, 2007), whereas Dennett’s formulation captures some of the universal I-ness which underlies all experience. Stapp (1993) defines consciousness more wordily as “[t]hat luminescent presence of coming-into-beingness that constitutes our inner world of experience” (p. 234).

Mind and body

A constant current of thought ever since philosophy began has been dualism: that we are a mind inhabiting a body, between which there is two-way traffic (Anastopoulos, 2021; Chalmers,

2007; Popper & Eccles, 1977; Robinson, 2018). Many people naturally gravitate to this model, although it has not been popular among modern philosophers and neuroscientists, who tend to favor a materialistic picture. But if there is more to existence than electrical signals propagating through neurons – just “atoms in the void” as Democritus put it – where do those mysterious qualia, the elements of sensation, come from? How can a neuron light up and give us the colour crimson or the taste and aroma of tea? A number of thinkers are willing to take on some form of dualism to explain this mystery, and a common theme here is quantum mechanics (Anastopoulos, 2021; Atmanspacher, 2020; de Barros & Montemayor, 2019; Gao, 2022; Hameroff & Penrose, 2014; Schwartz et al., 2005; Stapp, 2007).

The quantum theory of consciousness under focus here (Bell, 2023) is based on the same anatomical units identified by both Stapp (2017) and Eccles (1990). It brings together the elements of cortical anatomy, neurophysiology, philosophy, and quantum physics identified by them and adds a specific elaboration involving feedback cooling. It ends up as a well-specified model in which the conscious human brain is, in essence, a quantum computer built on top of a neural computer. Although physically based, the model allows room for the mind to exist as a coherent quantum entity spread macroscopically across the cortex like a superconducting sheet, and here we examine the implications raised by the curious case of sleepwalking. Is a sleepwalker a true philosophical zombie, and if so how can this be interpreted in terms of the new model? How can we give clarity to the notion of consciousness being switched on and off?

The key new element added here is feedback cooling, which makes it possible for thermal noise in the cortex to be reduced to the point where macroscopic quantum phenomena can operate at body temperature. Eccles called his basic units ‘dendrons’ or ‘psychons’, while Stapp called these same units ‘cortical minicolumns’, but both saw them as neuronal assemblies that were capable of generating consciousness quantum mechanically. Curiously, they never referenced each other’s work. Additional details are provided in Bell (2023), where the assemblies are described in more modern terms, saying they act in the manner of a quantum accelerator, a commercially available type of quantum computer that supercharges a standard computer. The claim is that when the accelerator is idle, as in sleep, the brain is a neural computer operating unconsciously, but when switched on, the psychons or minicolumns light up, computing power multiplies, and consciousness arises.

The modern refinement is that consciousness can be switched on or off by feedback cooling applied to these core neural units. In terms of physics, feedback cooling is an established technique that allows amplifiers to act as refrigerators (Kawamura & Kanegae, 2016;

Manikandan & Qvarfort, 2023), meaning it may be possible to create a macroscopic Bose–Einstein condensate and allow quantum computation to take place in a warm and noisy brain.

According to the model, consciousness is a property of the macroscopic quantum phenomenon which accompanies that cooling-induced transition. Noteworthy features of the model are that it explains how a quantum computer can operate at body temperature, how and why consciousness evolved, and is testable (Bell, 2023). Room-temperature quantum accelerators are now commercially available (Doherty, 2021), but the idea here is that nature got there first.

Consciousness and quantum mechanics

Not only does a quantum computer provide greater quantities of processing power, but, in the context of the mind, it might also supply the underlying unity of experience that has long attracted physicists such as Stapp, Penrose, and Bohm, neuroscientists like Eccles, and a number of contemporary philosophers (Gao, 2022). Macroscopic quantum phenomena are distinctive in that although spatially nonlocalised they exist all at once, just like consciousness appears to be (Marshall, 1989; Simon, 2019). Our conscious mind – the I – is able to take in a multitude of sights, sounds, sensations, thoughts, and memories, all available for instant access (Nagel, 2012).

There has therefore been growing interest in the idea that quantum mechanics offers a solution to the longstanding and perplexing problem of how minds and bodies interact. The field is large and growing, but key works pointing in this direction are Al-Khalili and McFadden (2014); Atmanspacher (2020); Penrose (2022); Chalmers and McQueen (2023); Josephson (2019); and Hameroff (2022). But if the mind is quantum mechanical, the crucial question is how can it sustain itself against the decoherence of thermal noise? This is where the feedback cooling model has the potential to fill in a major piece of the puzzle.

A feature of the feedback cooling model (Bell, 2023) is that it provides a clear demarcation between the conscious and the unconscious, one that matches common experience and which, in theory, can be experimentally verified. It aligns with the electrophysiological evidence that consciousness is accompanied by the presence of certain EEG features – notably 40 Hz thalamocortical oscillations – which are absent when a person is unconscious. These oscillations are seen here as reflecting the activation of the necessary cooling circuits. It should be noted that the very same features that are present during wakefulness are also present

during dreaming, albeit of a different kind. That is, qualia only arise when one is conscious, so that wakefulness, dreaming, and meditation are three different conscious states.

Unconsciousness, then, is a total lack of qualia, and during deep sleep, when both 40 Hz activity and rapid eye movements (REM) are absent, cooling circuits are switched off.

Applying these ideas to the curious issue of sleepwalking, the evidence is that sleepwalking occurs during the deepest stage of sleep (slow wave sleep, SWS), exactly when there are no eye movements and no 40 Hz signal. The implication is that, despite their physical activity, sleepwalkers are totally unconscious – experiential blanks – and the purpose of this paper is to explore that remarkable state of affairs. If true, it would have deep implications for the philosophy of mind and the brain–mind question. Likewise, if it should turn out that sleepwalkers are actually philosophical zombies – that is, beings which look and act like ordinary people but are actually unconscious (Kirk, 2023) – this would strongly reinforce the feedback cooling model. Being awake, one could then say, is a special quantum state built on top of an unconscious neural state. When the neural computer is operating by itself, everything happens “in the dark”, but when feedback cooling is applied and the system becomes macroscopically coherent, the system “lights up” (quantum mechanically speaking). The person is then fully conscious and at the controls of a quantum computer.

These possibilities motivate this paper. If sleepwalking is truly an unconscious state, it can be seen as the reflexive operation of a neural computer, one that enables us to turn over in bed during sleep and perform other subconscious bodily functions. But can this idea be sustained in the context of a person getting up in the night, raiding the refrigerator, getting a glass of water, and coming back to bed – all done totally unconsciously? Are such feats executed entirely within the operating limits of a neural computer (when released from the inhibitory circuits that normally prevent muscle activity during REM sleep), and what more does it require for someone to be conscious? Can the conscious human mind truly be an instance of a quantum computer?

After exploring such questions, the present work suggests that feedback cooling of the cortical minicolumn is a realistic, albeit provocative, idea worthy of further investigation. The idea of a quantum accelerator – a quantum computer able to operate on top of a conventional computer – appears to fit the physical facts and there is reason to think it could actually work within the brain’s cortical units. The plan here is to look closely at what sleepwalkers actually do and see whether it is reasonable to consider that their actions – some very sophisticated – reflect the outer limits of a neural computer.

We look at some actual remarkable cases, and consider whether driving a car is something a neural computer would be capable of? How about sending a text message? Gardening? According to the actual accounts of sleepwalkers, these activities are all done unconsciously, in the dark, raising the bar on what consciousness might actually be useful for.

As we will see, there are some key distinguishing marks between conscious and unconscious behaviour, and the feedback cooling model offers an insight into how useful consciousness might be. The conclusion reached is that there is prima facie evidence that sleepwalking involves an animated neural computer operating free of conscious control. That is, sleepwalking occurs when the brain, in a state of deep sleep, is released from the inhibitory circuits that, during REM sleep, prevent us from acting out our subconscious drives. More pointedly, this reveals a prime role for consciousness: it is there to sensibly weigh up and constrain unfettered activity of the automatic neural computer. In fact, most sleepwalkers express some degree of embarrassment or regret over their out-of-control nocturnal activity, saying it fails to align with their true selves.

Within that context, let us now look more closely at the difference between being conscious and being unconscious.

Conscious and unconscious

Consider now a person who in their waking moments possesses both mind and body. If they should fall into deep sleep and, due to the lack of inhibitory circuits present at this time (Flanagan, 1995a; Revonsuo, 2006) become a sleepwalker, the question before us is: can it be truly said that the sleepwalker is unconscious and that their body is operating automatically – in the dark – while their conscious mind is completely absent? This section addresses the question and suggests that the answer is yes.

To begin, a valuable perspective on the matter has been set out by Owen Flanagan, and is based on reflections about sleep, dreams, and zombies (Flanagan, 1995b). It addresses the key question of how consciousness relates to matter and what the evolutionary advantages of being conscious are.

It is helpful to first consider two realms, the classical and the quantum. This paper wants to establish the possibility that there is a gateway between the two and that it is opened and shut by feedback cooling. Al-Khalili and McFadden (2014) present a picture (their p. 314) of a living

cell being like a ship afloat on a thermodynamic sea, tossed back and forth by thermal noise, but ultimately being connected to the quantum world on the sea floor. In these terms, the classical brain, warm and wet, is tossed around by thermal vibrations, but by making use of feedback cooling, it can establish a coherent connection to the quantum realm. When it does, we have access to a remarkable non-classical world governed by quantum phenomena – nonlocality, entanglement, and all that they imply – which brings us a unified consciousness filled with feelings, colours, sounds, odors, thoughts, and all the other furniture of awareness. We have the familiar sense of ‘here I am’. Consciousness opens the doors of perception, where we find all the things that philosophers call qualia.

That sense of I means that, together with the intricate neural machinery inside our brain, we also have a mind which, during wakefulness, works seamlessly with it. The question then arises, why isn’t everything done subconsciously, in the dark? The brain is a structure that seems perfectly capable of working away unconsciously, all by itself, supplying the processing power to receive signals from our senses and issue commands to our muscles.

As we know, there is much that can be done subconsciously, and the prime example is the sleepwalker, a case originally raised by Flanagan. The sleepwalker can go to the fridge in the middle of the night, fill a glass of water from a tap, eat a snack, and return to bed – all done with total lack of awareness, as later paragraphs will document. Be that as it may, this paper suggests that if positive feedback is applied to a certain part of our cortex, an astounding change occurs: we suddenly become awake, and our senses are filled with a cornucopia of qualia, all simultaneously accessible to our awareness and able to be willingly acted upon. We have entered the quantum realm, a realm in which we have an insider’s front-row seat.

On this picture, the outstanding feature of consciousness is that it bestows immense processing power. Just like the add-on quantum accelerator, it multiplies processing power manifold, allowing multiple inputs and outputs to be simultaneously processed. We become the operator of an awake quantum computer, not a fumbling sleepwalker. We are the so-called ‘ghost in the machine’ (Revonsuo, 1993), which not only receives inputs from all over the body but can issue commands which allow the gymnast to execute a triple somersault with twist in just the way they imagined. The fast quantum computer sits on top of the classical neural computer, an architecture that allows our minds to program our brains: with practice, our minds can consolidate neural pathways so that things can be learnt and done automatically, subconsciously. Likewise, our conscious mind has direct access to all the “hard-wired” memory traces laid down in our brain over a lifetime. And it is all done seamlessly because the

anatomical substrate of both realms is exactly the same – the cortical minicolumn – although in one case an additional feedback circuit is at work.

We have said that the extra ingredient that consciousness brings is a boost in processing power. In practice this means we can quickly assess the favourability of several possible outcomes, bringing to bear complex esthetic and moral judgements. An added bonus is the facility to enjoy that power, as we quietly take in a glowing sunset, drink wine, or listen to a symphony. This is where human creativity comes in, whether painter, photographer, novelist, musician, dancer, poet, or scientist. It is the inspiration which drives us as we look out upon the physical world. It is the reason we are conscious.

Sleepwalkers

Despite there being multiple theories of consciousness (Adams & Petruccione, 2020; de Barros & Montemayor, 2019; Gao, 2022; Lenharo, 2024; Simon, 2019), few of them have actually addressed what the benefits of being conscious are. However, of direct relevance is a rich literature on philosophical zombies, creatures who are supposed to have all the faculties of conscious humans, save consciousness (Kirk, 2023). Although they lack qualia, they are still assumed to display all the functions of normal humans. This paper takes the view that such an assumption is wrong: a zombie is severely compromised by lack of computing power. Without a quantum accelerator, it will be slow and clumsy, and these are precisely the qualities traditionally ascribed to Haitian zombies. If real-life zombies did exist, they would be easily distinguished from real-life humans: they would have a glazed look, stumble along, and be bad conversationalists. They would probably also make bad philosophers. They would be exactly like sleepwalkers.¹

For some reason, sleepwalkers have not been much discussed by philosophers, but in fact sleepwalking is a very curious phenomenon that repays close attention (Flanagan, 1995a, 1996; Revonsuo, 2006). The contention here is that if one is looking for beings devoid of qualia, it is much more fruitful to consider sleepwalkers, not zombies.² Crucially, sleepwalkers indubitably

¹ Revonsuo (1996) has distinguished weak and strong degrees of zombiehood. While both are unconscious states, Revonsuo requires that the strong version involve the ability to carry out nonroutine tasks, make new decisions, and apply meaning (p. 387). But those are just the skills that consciousness brings. We cannot be both conscious and unconscious at the same time.

² Stapp (1993) recognised that sleepwalking is a distinct, unconscious state. When defining consciousness (p. 234) he notes that it “is extinguished during dreamless sleep ... [and is] ... absent in the state of somnambulism.” Penfield (1975) discussed the similar behaviour of patients undergoing petit mal seizures who are “totally unconscious”, even though they are capable of continuing well-rehearsed

exist – they are real people who, after a restless night’s sleep, wake to become normal human beings who can report what they’ve been through – and they provide valuable insights into the difference that consciousness makes.

The literature on sleepwalking is mostly in neurological journals, specifically those dealing with sleep behaviour disorders (SBDs). A useful review (Castelnovo et al., 2018) classifies sleepwalking as a sleep parasomnia characterised by incomplete arousal from deep sleep – the deepest stage of non-rapid eye movement (NREM) sleep (Flanagan, 1996; Hobson et al., 2000; Llinas & Paré, 1991; Nielsen, 2000).³ During episodes of sleepwalking, there is an absence of rapid eye movement but, importantly, the muscles controlling body movement remain active (the atonia that normally prevents us from moving during sleep and acting out our dreams is absent) (Flanagan, 1995a). This means that complex movements and behaviours are still possible, even though the sleepwalker is more or less unresponsive to their surroundings and their behaviour is “dissociated from awareness” (Castelnovo et al., 2018, p.471). That is, although the sleepwalker must be making use of sensory feedback in order to walk,⁴ they are operating completely in automatic mode – below the threshold of consciousness – and they typically go back to bed and “continue sleeping without reaching conscious awareness at any point” (loc. cit.). In the morning, they have no memory of the episode (Cartwright, 2010; Oudiette et al., 2009).⁵ There may also be somniloquy (sleep-talking), with slow speech and inappropriate responses to questions (Arkin, 1991). It is estimated that perhaps 2% of adults sleepwalk, although the proportion is about 20% in children aged 2 to 6 years (Plazzi et al., 2005).

patterns of activity, such as driving or playing the piano; Searle (1992) was struck by these cases and wondered why all behaviour couldn’t be unconscious, and concluded that consciousness provided extra “flexibility and creativity” (p. 108).

³ Sleep is conventionally divided into four stages: stage 1, which is REM sleep, when rapid eye movements and dreamily frequently co-occur, and three others, stages 2, 3, and 4 of progressively deeper non-REM (NREM) sleep (Revonsuo, 2006). The stages progress cyclically throughout the night. Stage 4, the deepest stage, is also known as delta sleep or slow wave sleep (SWS) in which the EEG is dominated by low-frequency delta waves. The key point is that sleepwalking occurs during the stages when mentation is at its lowest (and, from evidence discussed later, is arguably absent, at least on the occasions that we take as paradigms of the unconscious neural computer).

⁴ Indeed, a reported way of inducing sleepwalking is to lift someone who is in delta sleep onto their feet (Fisher et al., 1973). Again, we make use of sensory feedback to turn over in bed multiple times a night, without needing to wake. By way of contrast, in response to a full bladder, most people wake, get up, and go to the bathroom. Why wake? Consider that sleepwalkers, especially young ones, are known to relieve themselves (albeit in inappropriate places) and go back to bed, all without waking (Castelnovo et al. 2018).

⁵ Despite the title of Oudiette et al. (2009), its supplementary data gives the results of interviewing 6 unexceptional sleepwalkers (those without sleep terrors) and they indicate that, *over a lifetime*, only 2 could recall even a single dream or mental content during sleepwalking.

In the 12th and 13th centuries it was believed that during sleepwalking the soul split from the body and was temporarily elsewhere (Sukel, 2019). In the 1300's, Pope Clement V absolved sleepwalkers from moral responsibility for actions their bodies may have committed while sleepwalking, an absolution that still applies in the legal systems of a number of countries (Broughton et al., 1994). We are reminded of Lady Macbeth (Figure 1), of whom it was said: “her eyes are open” ... “aye, but their sense is shut,” or in more modern terms, in a state of zombiehood. These perspectives deserve more consideration, for as Chalmers (2023) notes, whereas conscious beings are moral agents, unconscious ones are not.

Figure 2. Lady Macbeth sleepwalking. The doctor remarks “You see, her eyes are open”, to which the lady-in-waiting replies “Aye, but their sense is shut”. In more modern terms, Lady Macbeth is a philosophical zombie. It is a case where consciousness, or a lack of it, “sticks out like a sore thumb” (Dennett, 2005, p. 178). Painting, undated lithograph c. 1900 by Artus Scheiner (www.meisterdrucke.com).

A personal account from a sleepwalker is illuminating (Hammond, 2012). She recounts how she sometimes gets out of bed in the middle of the night and wanders around her flat, all the while remaining fast asleep. In the morning she doesn't recall a thing, relying on third-party reports of what happened. She describes how sleepwalkers tend to have open eyes but a glazed

expression; they move around, usually in the dark, navigating largely from memory. Hammond relates how on one occasion she suddenly woke when she clumsily smashed a glass while filling it from a tap.

A medical case (Broughton et al., 1994) describes a sleepwalker who left the house and drove 23 km, through traffic lights, and stabbed his mother-in-law to death, all while in deep sleep. He was acquitted of murder on the basis of somnambulism. Another publication (Schenck & Mahowald, 1995) is noteworthy in describing cases where pain is totally absent during sleepwalking. Pain is commonly taken as a paradigm of qualia, but in this report we learn that a sleepwalker fractured bones in their hand from violent punches and sustained deep lacerations from kicking a door – all without experiencing pain or waking up. It was only when they woke in the morning that pain set in. It does not seem credible to explain this by saying that the individual experienced qualia – excruciating pain – at the time but then simply forgot them.⁶

Another interesting case concerns the case of a woman who was a keen gardener. She was mystified to wake one morning and discover she had dirt under her fingernails and fresh zucchinis in the refrigerator (pers. comm.).

I have spoken to a sleepwalker who relates how she sent a text message to her husband, copied for good measure to visiting friends, in which she complained, in rude and garbled language, that they had the TV on too loud. She has no memory of sending it, and finds it hard to believe (but for the irrefutable evidence on her phone) that she would ever send such a message. She does remember going to bed early and being annoyed at the loudness of the television.

Are NREM dream reports counterevidence?

It is true that sometimes vague sorts of memories can sometimes be recalled if an ordinary sleeper is woken during NREM sleep and asked to report whether they were dreaming (Herman et al., 1978; Kahn et al., 1997; Schenck & Mahowald, 1995). Such reports of vague feelings might be interpreted as evidence that the sleeper is experiencing qualia, but here we set out reasons why that does not apply to cases of sleepwalking.

First, it should be noted that most reports of awakenings from NREM sleep lump together all three stages, including the lighter ones (Nielsen, 2000). However, sleepwalking only occurs

⁶ It seems that reports of pain in dreams are rare (Nielsen et al. 1993).

during stages 3 and 4, which is deep sleep, a stage from which it is very hard to be woken. In fact, it is recommended that waking not be attempted, as it can prompt confusion and a violent reaction (Cartwright, 2010; Sukel, 2019). Nevertheless, even if we confine ourselves to just normal sleepers, it is true that if they are awakened during stages 3 and 4 they occasionally give reports of vague feelings. The important point is that, numerically, such reports are in the minority (generally less than 50% of awakenings; Nielsen (2000)). That is, most reports find “mentation” is absent in stages 3 and 4, and it is this result that is worth noting.

The negative reports align with the “common sense view” (Flanagan, 1997, p.68) that sleep is generally a state of unconsciousness and for the most part neural activity in the brain is below the threshold of consciousness. Francis Crick expresses it by saying that during deep sleep the mind is “totally blank, thoughtless, and senseless” (ibid.). Eccles believed that in sleep there is “abject annihilation of consciousness” (Eccles, 1961). Flanagan relates how at least one prominent sleep researcher believes that the case for dreaming in the deepest sleep – delta sleep or NREM stage 4 (when sleepwalking is most common) – is hard to make. Although Flanagan himself wishes to take a contrary view, he is prepared to admit that at least some sleeping may be dreamless, and this is what we wish to focus on.

The point is that deep sleep is the paradigm of what we see as an unconscious neural computer. In normal people deep sleep certainly contains blank episodes, and even more so do we expect this to apply to sleepwalkers, who are so deeply asleep that they are almost impossible to arouse (Cartwright, 2010). A strong indicator of lack of qualia is that sleepwalkers appear to feel no pain (Schenck & Mahowald, 1995) and after the episode they typically have no memory of it (Cartwright, 2010; Revonsuo, 2006).

At certain times, however, it is acknowledged that consciousness may seep through – a spot of cooling may take place – at which point some “mentation” may occur (Weinstein et al., 1991) and a dream report of some kind recorded.⁷ The exact boundary between the conscious and the unconscious, like the border between awake and asleep, is hard to define and the subject of much debate (Hobson et al., 2000; Pagel, 2000; Revonsuo, 1993). As Herman et al. (1978) say, “the study of when dreaming occurs in sleep has produced the most confusing literature of any

⁷ At times dreams may become so vivid that they reach conscious awareness; they can even wake us up and be remembered next morning. Generally, such instances originate during REM sleep when the brain is “autoactivated” while external input and motor output are actively suppressed (Kahn et al. 1997). In an influential paper, Crick and Mitchison (1983) set out a theory of why dreaming occurs, and here it is significant that they freely use the term “unconscious dream”: as they put it “dreaming ... only reaches normal consciousness if the sleeper wakes.” They suggest that “remination” may be a better word to use for unconscious dreaming.

in the sleep field ... [boiling down to] ... whether or not (and to what extent) dreaming occurs in NREM sleep” (p. 59). The difficulty is compounded by the occurrence of so-called lucid dreaming in which the dreamer appears to be aware they are dreaming and is able to control the direction and content of their dream (Kahan & LaBerge, 2011). We won’t enter the debate here, but our claim is that a clear paradigm case exists: that a sleepwalker is totally unconscious and that they are effectively acting out the preprogrammed actions of an unconscious neural computer. Kahn et al. (1997) say that “in delta NREM sleep there is little evidence of any high frequency activity... and NREM anomalies such as sleepwalking... are automatic *non-conscious* behaviours (p. 19, emphasis added). They add that “[t]hese abnormal NREM actions are non-conscious because conscious actions require activated cortical networks” (ibid.). We are not denying that some neural activity happens in the brain during sleep, but we do wish to claim that such mentations which arise from them are usually below conscious thresholds and usually require priming by waking the subject in order to make their memory traces accessible to consciousness. It has been suggested, for example, that mentation might be induced by the arousal process itself (Nielsen, 2000). As in all branches of science, measurement perturbs the system being measured.

In connection with the subject and her SMS activities mentioned above, she does sometimes remember isolated sensations, such as when a red light on a wall transformed into a laser beam emerging from a monster’s eye, but such an instance could have arisen from a lighter stage of sleep or from an unusually vivid mentation that was sufficiently strong to break through into consciousness.

In summary, all presumed counterexamples do not rule out the core proposition put forward here: that there are at least *some* cases (and probably more) of people being able to sleepwalk while being total mental blanks. The evidence points strongly to there being at least one pure instance – the paradigm – which demonstrates the surprisingly sophisticated, albeit limited, abilities of an unconscious neural computer. As Flanagan (1995a, p.13) notes, “sleepwalking without awareness could be possible ... No one knows for sure.” Again, Revonsuo (2006, p. 399) believes that there at least some instances where subjective consciousness has been completely lost.

Scientific investigation will no doubt help to resolve the issue. For example, an experiment using single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) during a sleepwalking episode (Bassetti et al., 2000) showed a pronounced lack of activity in thalamocortical circuits. The SPECT results were neatly summarised as “a dissociation between body sleep and mind sleep”

(ibid., p. 484) – a description that, if true, makes sleepwalking a perfect test case for seeing how body behaves in the absence of mind.

The absent accelerator

The foregoing has made the case that subconscious processing can occur at a remarkably high level, but that to become conscious something extra is needed. What might that key ingredient be?

The distinctive feature of sleepwalking is that body movements are slow. Walking is slow, actions are slow and clumsy, speech is slow and indistinct, typing is full of mistakes – just the sort of symptoms one might expect if the processing power of a computer controlling a robot were suddenly compromised. The frame rate of its display would plunge – similar perhaps to what might be expected if a standard computer were to somehow lose its accelerator. Lacking consciousness, and relying only on subconscious brain circuits, the sleepwalker is forced to act slowly as it executes “pre-programmed behaviour” (Broughton et al., 1994). No wonder the eyes are glazed, the face expressionless, memory absent – the somnambulist, as with Lady Macbeth, is in deep sleep. In other words, it can be said that there is *nothing it is like* to be a sleepwalker, no feeling of *here-I-am*.

EEG studies have shown that the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus of sleepwalkers are profoundly disengaged, reflecting automatic behaviour and inactive memory circuits (Krouse, 2022).⁸ Importantly, the distinctive 40 Hz oscillation between thalamus and cortex, a marker of qualia being present (when awake or in REM sleep), is decidedly missing (Bassetti et al., 2000; Flanagan, 1995a, 1996; Kahn et al., 1997; Llinas & Paré, 1991). We conclude that the temperature of the minicolumns is above the threshold where macroscopic quantum coherence can take place, and therefore the sleepwalker is unconscious. The result is that sleepwalkers put themselves in “great danger, given the absence of conscious control, awareness, and perceived pain” (Castelnovo et al., 2018, p.478). Having no qualia is a risky state of affairs (Schenck & Mahowald, 1995; Schenk et al., 1989), even if automatic

⁸ Compromised memory could mean that sleepwalkers are conscious but unable to remember their episodes, although this would be difficult to confirm experimentally and opens up a whole new philosophical area of debate.

mechanisms (involving both afferent and efferent nerve traffic) allow complex manoeuvres to be performed.⁹ The analogy is with stimuli sensed through blind-sight (Revonsuo, 2006, p.368).

We need much more research on sleepwalkers, blind-sight, and memory in order to chart the limits of subconscious processing (Derrien et al., 2022). Is there truly nothing it is like to be a sleepwalker? Revonsuo (1995) discusses the issue and favours the idea that there can be “double dissociation” between consciousness and perceptual input, so that either can exist without the other. There can be behaviour based on conscious “explicit” information or on unconscious “implicit” information. As an instance of the difference, Revonsuo draws attention to experiments where subjects volunteered to sleep with their eyelids open – they neither reported visual stimuli nor dreamt about them. Flanagan (1995a, p. 10) says “it is obscure whether, or in what precise sense, sleepwalkers and talkers are experiential blanks,” and this aspect deserves further study. As Flanagan emphasises, if someone says they are conscious, that is self-evidently true. In contrast, it seems plain that a zombie is incapable of saying such a thing, and a similar impossibility also seems true of a sleepwalker. It would be impossible for a sleepwalker, or a sleeptalker for that matter, to utter the words, I am conscious.¹⁰

Zombies

This brings us back to zombies, who (or which) have occupied a large philosophical literature (see Seager (n.d.) and its references). An accessible and wide-ranging perspective into the workings of zombies and how they relate to conscious beings has also been given by Kirk (1974) and Revonsuo (2006, p.383). Of direct relevance to the model of consciousness set out here is Kirk’s consideration of what it might be like to be “Zulliver” – a parallel to the Gulliver of *Gulliver’s Travels* except that his brain has been invaded by technologically advanced microscopic beings far smaller than Lilliputians. These creatures are able to disconnect his brain from his nerves, and then monitor the ascending nerves, the afferents, and stimulate the descending fibres, the efferents, so as to recreate behaviour indistinguishable from the human Gulliver. Zulliver acts like what Kirk calls a “super-puppet, with resident puppeteers”. The clever invaders use sophisticated algorithms to analyse incoming nerve traffic and compute

⁹ Llinas & Paré (1991) call attention to what they call the central paradox of REM sleep. Stimuli which are readily perceived when awake generally do not awaken subjects in REM sleep, even though the primary evoked cortical responses, recorded electrically, are considerably higher than in the waking state (ibid., p. 524). That is, the 40 Hz circuits have the ability to override other brain activity. They also remind us that cartoleptics can suddenly fall asleep during the day, presumably due to a faulty on/off switch.

¹⁰ Although it is claimed that lucid dreamers can signal, using pre-agreed eye movements, that they are consciously dreaming (see Revonsuo, 1995).

what outgoing signals are needed to produce the required behaviour. The point is that no-one would want to say that Zulliver was conscious, even though his behaviour was similar to his pre-invasion state. He would, in fact, be a machine, a zombie. Elsewhere in his argument, Kirk alludes to, but does not take up, cases of sleepwalking and sleeptalking, even though it would seem that the parallels are exact.

The crucial difference between Gulliver and Zulliver, I suggest, is that Gulliver carries a quantum computer in his head whereas Zulliver is limited to whatever common or garden computing power the invaders have been able to assemble. The consideration here is that, to work like a human, the necessary computing power needs to be immense: the information from each afferent nerve has to be shared with every other afferent nerve and the ensuing output state computed in real time so as to produce a driving signal for an efferent nerve, each one of which also has to be considered in relation to all the others. It is a formidable task, and without almighty computing power poor Zulliver is left as slow and mindless as a zombie, a sleepwalker. It is a magical gift that we have a mind, a quantum accelerator, that can compute all the inputs and outputs and act – smoothly and seamlessly – like a sentient, thinking, speaking, living human. Seager (n.d.) makes the point that the logical possibility that zombies might exist automatically refutes physicalism, for if there were an entity having the same physical properties as me, but none of my mental properties, then the assertion that everything is ultimately physical must be false. The argument is even stronger when applied to sleepwalkers, for unlike zombies, such beings indeed exist and can be found all around us.¹¹ The fundamental difference between a sleepwalker and the same person when awake is that the former is (temporarily) unconscious, while the latter, of course, is gloriously awake.

Kirk uses his discussion of Zulliver to argue that there is something about human beings which materialism leaves out. Briefly, the missing ingredient is self-awareness. A mind has a unified experience of its multiple inputs and outputs (except for certain unconscious functions controlled by the autonomic nervous system), and is powerful enough that it can operate in real time to judge and choose what the next moment should bring.

A virtue of the feedback cooling model is that it provides a single locus where the neural computer and the quantum computer come together. As sought by Revonsuo (1995), there is just one site – the cortical minicolumn – that consciousness can call home: there is no additional Cartesian theatre or multiple drafts, and there is no binding problem. “The

¹¹ Seager notes that “it is logically possible that I might become a zombie in the next instant.” A stronger, more empirical statement is that I could well become a sleepwalker after I go to bed tonight.

experienced world [needs to be] fundamentally one,” he says, “there is no room for differentiating objects from subjects or duplicating anything” (p. 48).¹² Through cooling, the sensory apparatus in the brain is brought into intimately connection with the quantum realm and all its latent possibilities, including, it is conjectured, consciousness.

Consciousness, we assert, has immense power because it is in just the right place to mediate between the physical world and the quantum world, between input and output. Consciousness is a representation of the world and all its possibilities and can compute what is needed to make its owner move forward in life. By existing it enables mathematics, science, literature, art, and all other creative endeavours. An interesting question following on from this is whether a quantum robot (Benioff, 1998) could ever be conscious. Our response would be no, because the robot is not poised quantum mechanically between inputs and outputs as minicolumns are. Consciousness relies on our minds being poised at the pinnacle between efferents and afferents, and feedback cooling is the key to its awakening.

Recapitulation

The foregoing has assembled a novel but credible picture of what might be the fundamental difference between the conscious and unconscious states, the paradigms of each being that of an awake person and that same individual when sleepwalking. The suggested answer involves a transition from unconscious neural computer to conscious quantum computer, brought about by means of feedback cooling.

There is a seamless transition from one type of computer to the other because they both share one and the same basic hardware – the cortical minicolumn. When thalamocortical circuits are inactive, the minicolumns act individually and unconsciously, but when switched on the units combine – their wave functions overlap – to form a macroscopically coherent, and awake, cortical sheet. The resulting conscious ‘I’ encompasses all of those units and can simultaneously access all their information content. Quantum nonlocality performs the necessary binding, so there is no need for a central spot in the brain where consciousness arises. “Nobody is looking for another pineal gland,” as Revonsuo (1993) expresses it.

¹² As noted earlier, Revonsuo (2006) requires what we see as an impossibly severe criterion for a sleepwalker to be in strong zombiehood – that they be indistinguishable from a conscious person. On pp. 387–391 he gives five examples from the literature of possible zombiehood, of which none receive more than a “weak” zombiehood rating, even though *unconscious* activity is described. Nevertheless, we do read (p. 399) that “in a few cases [of automatism] we have good reason to believe subjective consciousness to have been completely lost” (p. 399), which is actually the paradigm being sought here.

All the minicolumns are at just the right spot to be causally efficacious: at the pinnacle of efferent (sensory) and afferent (motor) nerve pathways. The mind is then in a position to receive sensory input, generate a coherent macroscopic quantum state, and execute motor action. The units “light up” (quantum mechanically speaking), and the aggregate of grey matter awakes. The brain, once in a state of sleep, experiences the light of consciousness which, in philosophical terms, is made up of all its associated qualia. The sleepwalker awakens from zombiehood.

This paper raises intriguing philosophical questions about minds and bodies, and whether monism or dualism may be the more apt philosophical position. The existence of a quantum consciousness – a self – over and above the body it inhabits is a long-standing and thorny question, but the feedback cooling model provides a fixed reference point for considering whether mind and body are distinguishable entities. Both Stapp and Eccles were supporters of dualism (Popper & Eccles, 1977; Stapp, 2005), and here we give a more modern and perhaps realistic account of how mind could conceivably arise from matter. Although framed as a physical model, the considerations here provide a reasonable starting point for constructing an interactive dualism that both Stapp and Eccles may agree with. There is matter – atoms and molecules – on one side and a macroscopically coherent quantum state – bearing qualia – on the other. Moreover, the model helps us understand how there can be, in the one brain, a striking difference between the vivid presence and dark absence of phenomenal experience – a “phenomenal vacuum” (Revonsuo, 2003).

This is not the place to begin a detailed discussion of dualism, although arguments for and against can be found in Robinson (2018) and Mørch (2023). Powerful arguments against physicalism are given in Nagel (2012). Depending on interpretation, it may also be that neutral monists and panpsychists might find parts of the model attractive, although as Revonsuo (2003) argues, taking everything to be conscious in some degree does not let us understand the radical conscious–nonconscious contrast. The virtue of the feedback cooling model is that it provides a coherent account of how the mental could emerge from the material.

Conclusion

This text has explored a neurophysiological specific model of how consciousness could arise as a macroscopically coherent quantum state when cortical minicolumns are subject to feedback cooling. The particular focus has been on the contrast between what might be going on in cases of sleepwalking and in cases of being awake, and the suggested answer is that we

are seeing activity of the same neural machinery, the minicolumns, at work. The final outcomes might look similar, but it makes a vast difference whether feedback cooling circuits are switched on or off.

Although a range of detailed questions remain unanswered, the broad feedback cooling model does appear to offer a path forward. Does magnetic resonance thermometry provide us with a handle on consciousness – perhaps a potential consciousness meter? A study of whether the model provides a satisfactory account of what is going on in sleep, and especially sleepwalking, has the potential to strengthen our philosophical and neurophysiological understanding of a mysterious but fascinating condition and of consciousness itself.

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Declaration of competing interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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